

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TONI MORRISON'S "GOD HELP THE CHILD" AND ABDULLA QAHHOR'S "SAROB" NOVELS: SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES

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Abstract

This research paper presents a comparative analysis of Toni Morrison's "God Help the Child" and Abdulla Qahhor's "Sarob", two novels written in different cultural contexts but showing certain thematic and psychological parallels. The aim of this study is to explore the similarities and differences in how both novels tackle the impacts of childhood trauma, the inner struggles of their characters, and the societal pressures that shape their journeys. Through a detailed examination of the themes, writing styles, and character development in each novel, this article demonstrates how Morrison and A. Qahhor both address the complexities of human experiences, while also highlighting the distinct cultural frameworks that shape their narratives.

Keywords: English literature, Uzbek literature, trauma, Toni Morrison, Abdulla Qahhor, Karim, Bride

INTRODUCTION

Toni Morrison's "God Help the Child" and Abdulla Qahhor's "Sarob" are novels rooted in distinctly different sociopolitical and cultural situations. Morrison's work, set in contemporary America, focuses on racial discrimination and its psychological impacts, while Qahhor's novel, situated in Soviet-era Uzbekistan, critiques the social and political injustices of the time. Despite these differences, both novels share an exploration of how childhood experiences, social expectations, and inner psychological struggles shape the lives of their protagonists. This comparative analysis highlights both the similarities and differences between these two works, offering insights into how authors from different cultural backgrounds address universal themes of identity, trauma, and self-discovery.

This study employs a comparative literary analysis, including the themes of childhood trauma, the psychological development of the characters, and the societal influences in each novel. Key elements such as narrative style, thematic focus, and character evolution are compared to highlight both the commonalities and the distinct aspects of each text.

Similarities Between “God Help the Child” and “Sarob”

1. Impact of Childhood Experiences on Protagonists’ Adult Lives

Both “God Help the Child” and “Sarob” delve deeply into how childhood experiences shape the psychological and emotional development of the protagonists in adulthood. In “God Help the Child”, the protagonist, Bride, suffers from the trauma of being rejected by her mother due to her dark skin. This rejection leads to profound insecurities that persist into adulthood, manifesting as emotional distance and a deep sense of inadequacy. Similarly, in “Sarob”, Karim’s disillusionment with the idealistic dreams he held as a youth and unfairness of society, and the stark realities he faces in adulthood, create a profound internal conflict. His youthful idealism clashes with the harsh realities of Soviet life, causing psychological trauma.

2. Internal Struggles and Self-Discovery

Both novels emphasize the characters' inner struggles as they seek to reconcile their past with their present identities. Bride in “God Help the Child” begins a journey of self-discovery, trying to overcome the emotional scars left by her mother’s rejection and societal racism. Her quest for self-acceptance is central to the novel. In “Sarob”, Karim’s internal struggle revolves around his disillusionment with the ideals he once valued. His self-discovery involves recognizing the gap between his youthful dreams and the reality of his adult life. In both novels, the protagonists are driven by a need to understand themselves and the forces that have shaped their lives.

3. Societal Pressures and Their Influence on Identity

Society plays a significant role in shaping the identities of both Bride and Karim. In “God Help the Child”, societal views on race and skin color profoundly affect Bride’s self-worth. The racism she experiences as a dark-skinned Black woman in America leads to her internalizing negative stereotypes, which she must overcome to find peace. In “Sarob”, the Soviet regime’s ideological pressures and the pervasive social inequality contribute to Karim’s disillusionment. The ideals of the Soviet system, which once seemed attainable to Karim, are revealed to be flawed, leaving him grappling with a sense of betrayal and confusion about his place in society.

Differences Between “God Help the Child” and “Sarob”

1. Cultural and Sociopolitical Contexts

One of the most striking differences between the two novels is their cultural and sociopolitical settings. “God Help the Child” is set in contemporary America and deals primarily with issues of race, skin color, and social discrimination. The

novel reflects on the legacy of racism and how it continues to affect individuals in modern society. Bride's struggles with her dark skin serve as a commentary on America's persistent racial issues, highlighting how deeply ingrained these prejudices are.

In contrast, "Sarob" is set in Soviet-era Uzbekistan and focuses on the social and political challenges of that time. Karim's story reflects the disillusionment that many felt toward the Soviet system, which promised equality and justice but often failed to deliver. The novel critiques the disparity between socialist ideals and the lived reality of many citizens. While both novels address societal pressures, "Sarob" is more concerned with political and economic trauma, while "God Help the Child" focuses on race and personal trauma.

2. Writing Style and Narrative Structure

Morrison's "God Help the Child" incorporates elements of magical realism, a style for which she is well known. This is evident in Bride's physical regression into a child-like state as she struggles with her trauma, a symbolic representation of her emotional wounds. Morrison uses this mystical element to blur the lines between reality and metaphor, adding a layer of complexity to the psychological exploration of her characters.

In contrast, Qahhor's "Sarob" adheres to a more straightforward, realistic narrative style. Qahhor's prose is grounded in the social and political realities of Soviet Uzbekistan, with no elements of magical realism. His focus is on providing a realistic portrayal of the challenges faced by individuals within a flawed political system. This difference in narrative style reflects the distinct literary traditions from which each author emerges.

3. Themes of Race vs. Social Ideology

While both novels deal with societal pressures, the nature of these pressures differs greatly. In "God Help the Child", the primary issue is race and how societal views on skin color impact the character's life. The novel explores the psychological damage caused by racism, both within families and in society at large. Bride's experiences are shaped by her identity as a Black woman in a world that devalues her because of her dark skin.

On the other hand, "Sarob" centers on the clash between personal ideals and societal reality under Soviet socialism. Karim's trauma stems not from racial prejudice but from the failure of the political system to live up to its promises. His struggle is with the ideological gap between the socialist ideals he was raised to believe in and the corruption and inequality he witnesses as an adult.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, while “God Help the Child” and “Sarob” are rooted in different cultural and political contexts, they share significant thematic parallels, particularly in their exploration of childhood trauma, internal psychological struggles, and societal influences. Both novels depict protagonists who must navigate the lasting effects of their early experiences and the expectations placed on them by society. However, their differences—most notably in their focus on race versus ideology and their distinct narrative styles—highlight the unique concerns of the societies in which these works were created. By examining these similarities and differences, this comparative analysis sheds light on the universal nature of human struggle, while also emphasizing the importance of cultural context in shaping literary expression.

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